

Requirements on the attitude noise

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SAG_LL_020

The MMS study provides a power spectrum (PSD) of the attitude variations caused by the FEEP control loop, using measurements from the star tracker (positions) and PSM (rates). The PSD curve depends on the assumed control loop characteristics, and we do not have the final result yet.

In this note I start from the opposite side, and try to estimate what the acceptable PSD would be from the viewpoint of the final astrometric goal (i.e., $10 \mu\text{as}$ at $G = 15$ and a floor of $4 \mu\text{as}$ for bright stars). The approach is simple: given the photon noise errors and number of stars as function of magnitude, estimate how accurately the attitude could be determined in different frequency intervals. Also determine the contribution of each frequency interval to the final error budget. It will be found that this contribution is negligible below a certain frequency f_0 . This defines the highest frequency at which the attitude determination will be useful. The requirement is then that the actual attitude noise *above* the same frequency is negligible.

An elementary measurement consists of the mean star location in a single CCD crossing, taking 0.86 s. Thus all attitude variations with frequencies above $1/0.86 = 1.2$ Hz will be smoothed out and contribute to the error budget only through the PSF smearing. This is already taken into account in the accuracy analysis and is therefore not considered here.

Given a star density of N stars per square degree, the number of elementary measurements in a great-circle scan is roughly $30 \times 0.65^\circ \times 360^\circ \times N = 7020N$ (since there are in total 30 columns of CCDs in the two telescopes). However, I shall assume that only half of them, or $3500N$ measurements per great circle, are actually useful for the along-scan attitude determination (the other half may be binaries etc). For $N(G)$ the following approximate relation may be used:

$$N(G) = 0.025 \times 10^{0.25G} \quad (1)$$

(valid for $b = 90^\circ$ between $G = 12$ and 18). Star densities at the galactic pole are considered, since the performance of the attitude determination is (conservatively) set by the minimum star density rather than the mean density.

The photon noise σ_ξ of the elementary observation is about 20 times the final parallax error, and it can thus be found as function of G from Table 5 in SAG_LL_017. An analytical fit gives:

$$\sigma_\xi^2 = 6400 + 730u + 0.35u^2 \quad [\mu\text{as}^2] \quad (2)$$

where $u = 10^{0.4(G-10)}$.

Now let us consider the determination of attitude errors in a certain small bandwidth Δf around frequency f . It is assumed that this can be done by fitting harmonic functions of the spin angle in the course of the great circle scan. To do this successfully, considering the uneven distribution of real stars, requires an average of about 10 observations per cycle, or a rate of observations of at least $10/f$ per second. Over the spin period ($T = 10800$ s) this translates to a minimum of $108000f$ observations. With $3500N$ observations

per spin, the minimum star density is $N_{\min} = 30f \text{ deg}^{-2}$ and the minimum magnitude $G_{\min} = 12.4 + 4 \lg f$ according to (1). So we can in principle use all stars fainter than $G_{\min}$ to determine the harmonic terms in the considered frequency interval. The precision σ_h of each coefficient of a sine or cosine term is roughly given by $\sigma_h^{-2} = (1/2) \times \sum \sigma_\xi^{-2}$, where the sum is taken over all the observations. Thus,

$$\sigma_h^{-2} = \frac{1}{2} \int_{G_{\min}}^{G_{\max}} \frac{dN}{dG} \sigma_\xi(G)^{-2} dG \quad (3)$$

where we take $G_{\max} = 20$ (this limit has very little influence on the result, as long as it is greater than about 17). The total number of harmonic terms in the frequency interval is $2T\Delta f$, so the total power of the attitude uncertainty at any point is $T\Delta f \sigma_h^2$. It follows that the PSD at f is $P(f) = T\sigma_h^2$. A table of $P(f)$ is given below. The PSD depends weakly of f through the lower integration limit $G_{\min}$, but for $f < 1$ Hz one has an almost constant level of the order of $1000 \mu\text{as}^2\text{Hz}^{-1}$.

f [Hz]	0.0001	0.001	0.01	0.1	1	10
$P(f)$ [$\mu\text{as}^2\text{Hz}^{-1}$]	697	698	701	738	1188	7516

Note that $P(f)$ is the PSD of the attitude estimation error in the final data processing. This must be distinguished from the PSD of the actual attitude variations caused by the FEEP control. Let us assume that the latter PSD is $P_0(f) = Af^{-\alpha}$. If $P(f) = P$ (constant) the two PSD cross at $f_0 = (A/P)^{1/\alpha}$. In this case one would choose to estimate the attitude only up to the frequency f_0 , since for higher frequencies the actual variations are smaller than the estimation errors. The total RMS attitude error is then:

$$\sigma_{\text{att}}^2 = \int_0^{f_0} P(f) df + \int_{f_0}^{\infty} P_0(f) df = \frac{\alpha}{\alpha - 1} P f_0 \quad (4)$$

Conservatively, we take $\alpha = 2$. In order to reach the accuracy floor of $80 \mu\text{as}$ for bright stars (corresponding to $4 \mu\text{as}$ for the parallax), the attitude error should be small compared to that number, or less than (say) $10 \mu\text{as}$. With $P = 1000 \mu\text{as}^2\text{Hz}^{-1}$ this gives $f_0 < 0.05$ Hz.

Conclusion: Attitude errors probably need to be estimated up to a frequency of about 0.05 Hz. Below that frequency there is effectively no requirement on the PSD of the attitude variations. At 0.05 Hz the PSD of the attitude variations should not exceed $1000 \mu\text{as}^2\text{Hz}^{-1}$ and for higher frequencies it should decrease at least as f^{-2} . This defines an upper envelope for the power spectrum of attitude variations. It should be noted that this analysis is very rough and probably quite conservative.